

(FYM) was applied at 5 t dry weight/ ha in the main field. It contained 0.56% N, 0.13% P, and 0.75% K.

Azospirillum was applied at 2 kg/800 m² to the nursery area and 2 kg/ha to the main field during 1986 kharif (total 4 kg). In 1986 rabi, Azospirillum was applied 1 kg to seeds needed for 1 ha, 1 kg/ 800 m² to the nursery, 2 kg/800 m² as seedling root dip, and 2 kg/ ha to the main field (total 6 kg). Soil application to both nursery and main field was done by mixing 2 kg peat-based inoculant with 25 kg powdered FYM and 25 kg soil. This was uniformly broadcast in the

nursery at sowing and in the main field at transplanting. P and K were applied per soil test recommendation to all treatments. For all 4 treatment levels, N was applied as 59% basal and 50% in 2 equal splits at active tillering and panicle initiation.

During kharif, the main effect of biofertilizer and organic manure was not significant individually or in combination, but levels of N in the subplots were significant. Application of 98 kg N/ha gave significantly higher grain yield than other treatments and 30% higher than control (Table 1).

Productive tillers/m² was also significant for N level.

During rabi, the interaction of N level, organic manure, and biofertilizer application was significant for productive tillers and for grain yield. Combined application of organic manure, Azospirillum, and 100% recommended N resulted in significantly higher yield, on par with 100% N with Azospirillum (Table 2). The more pronounced effect of Azospirillum during rabi than during kharif may be due to its combined application to seed, soil, and roots. □

Screening azolla strains for shading tolerance

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In dual culture with rice, azolla growth is limited by light deficiency due to rice canopy shading. Beginning 30-40 d after transplanting, the rice crop severely suppresses azolla growth. With azolla strains tolerant of shading, biomass production could be improved and growth prolonged.

We screened 12 azolla strains for shading tolerance in a pot experiment.

Azolla was inoculated at 1.4 g fresh weight/ pot (197 g fresh weight/ m²) in 10-cm-diameter beakers and grown on soil-water culture. Triplephosphate was applied weekly. Light intensities of 50% and 15% were attained by shading beakers with green nylon screens (control was left unshaded), with 3 replications. Biomass of azolla was determined every 5 d for 5 wk, and days to biomass doubling computed for the period from inoculation to maximum biomass. Azolla N content at the end of the experiment was determined by micro-Kjeldahl method.

Tested azolla strains did not differ much in tolerance for shading (see table). Strains with the best growth

without shading (*A. caroliniana* #310, #311; *A. mexicana* #202; *A. microphylla* #401) also were the best strains with shading. Some strains were particularly well adapted or poorly adapted to shading. *A. microphylla* #417 and *A. caroliniana* #301 were less affected by shading; *A. pinnata* var. *pin.* #49 and #58 were much more affected. *A. filiculoides* #107 obviously was not adapted to tropical conditions and did not grow well.

The N content of the two strains that performed best (*A. caroliniana* #301, *A. mexicana* #202) was increased by shading. □

Effects of light intensity (100%, 50%, 15%) on growth and N content of 12 azolla strains. Pot experiment, IRRI, 1985.

Azolla strain	Accession no.	Maximum biomass ^a (g fresh wt/pot)			Doubling time (d)			N content (% N in dry wt)					
		100	50	15	100	50	15	100	50	15			
<i>A. pinnata</i> var. <i>imbricata</i>	5	10.07	def	8.53	cd	6.05	b	7.78	10.82	13.26	3.69	3.29	3.34
<i>A. pinnata</i> var. <i>imbricata</i>	49	11.66	bcd	8.01	de	4.71	cd	9.18	8.80	16.37	3.33	3.20	3.33
<i>A. pinnata</i> var. <i>imbricata</i>	58	9.21	efg	6.69	ef	3.62	d	8.33	9.87	20.37	3.52	3.37	3.81
<i>A. filiculoides</i>	107	7.38	gh	5.10	f	1.58	e	14.98	14.95	28.12	4.32	4.61	^b
<i>A. mexicana</i>	202	12.18	bc	13.29	a	7.89	a	8.99	8.63	11.27	4.01	4.17	4.55
<i>A. caroliniana</i>	301	6.76	h	7.94	de	4.17	cd	9.89	11.23	19.33	3.49	3.57	3.47
<i>A. caroliniana</i>	310	15.08	a	14.44	a	8.35	a	8.20	8.38	10.91	3.99	4.16	4.64
<i>A. caroliniana</i>	311	13.28	ab	13.30	a	7.59	a	8.63	8.64	11.83	4.30	4.01	4.04
<i>A. microphylla</i>	401	11.76	bcd	10.80	b	7.57	a	7.37	9.58	9.08	4.94	4.89	4.91
<i>A. microphylla</i>	417	8.18	fgh	9.96	bc	5.43	bc	8.71	9.91	14.46	4.45	4.51	4.26
<i>A. microphylla</i>	418	11.15	cde	9.36	bcd	5.38	bc	7.40	8.06	11.82	4.60	4.35	4.47
<i>A. pinnata</i> var. <i>pinnata</i>	701	9.53	ef	8.58	cd	5.00	bc	8.11	10.74	12.20	3.91	3.24	3.51
LSD (0.05)		1.94		1.71		1.33							

^aIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different by DMRT at the 5% level. ^bNot enough material for analysis.

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